

ORIGINAL RESEARCH ARTICLE

UNDERSTANDING DROWNING TRENDS: A STUDY OF RECENT CASES IN MUZAFFARNAGAR DISTRICT, INDIA

Pragati Jain^{1*}, Shefali Chaudhary¹, Poorvi Ujjainia¹,
Sneha K. Kochumon², Tania Debnath¹ Ashish kumar¹

1, Post Graduate, Department of Forensic Science, Chandigarh University, Ludhiana, Punjab

2 Assistant professor, Department of Forensic Science, Mohan Babu University, Tirupati

^{1}Corresponding Author: pragatijain980@gmail.com,*

Author contribution:

**all authors have equal contributions during manuscript preparation and declared no conflict of interest with any agency*

RECEIVED:
9 JULY 24

ACCEPTED:
9 AUGUST 24

PUBLISHED:
20, AUGUST 24

ABSTRACT

Drowning remains a significant public health challenge worldwide, causing approximately 362,000 fatalities annually, irrespective of socioeconomic status. This study focuses on analyzing critical drowning trends in Muzaffarnagar district, Uttar Pradesh, India, where drowning-related morbidity and mortality have a substantial impact. The analysis is based on data collected from 55 drowning cases reported from 2017 to 2022, sourced from RTI data, Muzaffarnagar. The findings reveal a significant gender disparity, with males disproportionately affected, consistent with broader trends observed in India. Accidental drowning emerges as the primary cause of incidents, highlighting the need for preventive measures and safety interventions in high-risk areas such as canals and ponds. Fluctuating trends across different police stations underscore the dynamic nature of this issue, necessitating localized strategies informed by local conditions. Challenges identified, including unidentified incidents and the absence of suicidal cases, underscore the importance of enhancing data collection and reporting mechanisms. The study emphasizes the critical role of multi-sectorial collaboration, public awareness campaigns, and evidence-based policy interventions in preventing drowning incidents. Initiatives such as the development of a national drowning prevention action plan by the National Disaster Response Force are essential for creating a safer environment and reducing the burden of drowning in Muzaffarnagar district and beyond.

Keywords: Drowning, Public health, Accidental drowning, multi-sectoral collaboration, Preventive measures etc.

1. INTRODUCTION

Drowning, which typically occurs in watery environment, continues to pose a significant public health challenge, resulting in approximately 362,000 fatalities annually globally, irrespective of socioeconomic status. This issue has been closely monitored by the World Health Organization (WHO) and its affiliated countries. (Armstrong & Erskine, 2018). Drowning-related morbidity and mortality have a significant impact on India, with risk factors identified for this setting like those within other low-income and middle-income countries (Lukaszyk et al., 2018). Drowning is defined as a process of experiencing respiratory impairment from submersion/immersion in a liquid medium. To delineate the incident's outcome, this is further divided into descriptive terms such as death, morbidity, and no morbidity. Wet drowning, dry drowning, and near-drowning are no longer acceptable terms, although they may still be used when discussing drowning. Drowning is a major public health problem, especially in children. Drowning usually occurs in a rapid fashion and is most often silent. Drowning can occur in both warm and cold water. In many cases, cold water can be protective especially in children. The most immediate threat in drowning is dysfunction of the cardiac and CNS systems. Hypoxemia and acidosis need to be corrected immediately if mortality is to be avoided. Even those who survive may develop a vegetative state due to the prolonged cerebral hypoxia (McCall & Sternard, 2017). Drowning accounts for more than 100 deaths per day or about 38,000 fatal casualties in a year in India. In June last year, the NDRF chief had said that out of the total annual deaths due to drowning, about two-thirds take place at the designated bathing 'ghats' or banks of rivers notified by the authorities (The Print, 2024). The present study focuses on discussing and examining the critical drowning trends in the district of Muzaffarnagar, Uttar Pradesh, India. During the time of field work in the local police stations in the district, it has been observed that the frequency of drowning cases was significantly high from 2017-2022. Total 55 cases of drowning have been discovered from RTI (Right to Information) data, Muzaffarnagar. The cases were reported in the different regional police stations of Khatauli, Bhopa, Kakrauli, New Mandi, Chhappar, Charthawal, Purkaaji, mansurpur, Sikhera etc.

2. DROWNING STUDIES OVER THE LAST FEW YEARS

Isaac et al. (2007) carried out a study at the Christian Medical College in Vellore. They found that drowning wasn't seen as a big cause of child deaths, even though many water bodies, like ponds, were risky because they weren't protected. They suggested solutions like educating the community, setting up day nurseries, and making water bodies safer. In the same year, Kanchan et al. (2007) researched cases of

near-drowning in Karnataka. They noticed that young boys under 10 were the most affected, and most drownings happened in freshwater. They stressed that these incidents could be prevented with supervised swimming and quick emergency help. Also, Shetty and Shetty (2007) studied drowning cases in Mangalore. They discovered that open wells and ponds lacked proper safety measures, which was a major issue. They called for better precautions, like putting barriers around wells, and suggested collecting more local data to help prevent future cases. Fast forward to 2018, Thakar et al. (2018) in Haryana found that middle-aged men were the most vulnerable to drowning, with most incidents happening in canals. They also noticed that drowning was more common during certain seasons. Dandona et al. (2019) focused on Bihar, using verbal autopsies to explore drowning deaths, especially in children. They found that many drowning cases went unreported, and in most cases, the victims were already deceased when found. Around the same time, Lukaszyk et al. (2019) focused at drowning in rural West Bengal, focusing on child drownings. They pointed out that children were often unsupervised around dangerous water sources, and recommended educating parents and forming village committees to communicate risks. Gupta et al. (2020) concentrated on the Sundarbans region, aiming to create a drowning prevention program. They identified policies and government programs that could help and stressed the importance of involving the community and addressing social issues. Teron and Paul (2020), studied drowning cases at Gauhati Medical College. They found that most victims were men and most drownings happened in freshwater. They emphasized the need for better prevention strategies. Shubhendu et al. (2020), studied drowning cases in Ranchi and found that men in rural areas were more likely to drown. Lakes were the most common drowning spots, and many victims were dealing with family or financial stress. Gupta et al. (2021) studied drowning in the Sundarbans region again, this time focusing on children. They reported a high number of deaths in children aged 1-2, with ponds near homes being the most common drowning sites. Finally, Siddiqui and Singh (2022) addressed a specific issue: bucket-related drowning in infants and toddlers in Indian households. They found that boys between 12-18 months were the most affected and recommended injury prevention counseling to tackle the problem.

3. AIM OF THE STUDY

The main objective of this research article is to provide a demographic data signifying the trends of drowning cases in the district of Muzaffarnagar, India with respect to gender of the victim, location of drowning, source of drowning, mode of drowning and police station wise distribution of drowning cases from the year of 2017 to 2022.

4. METHODOLOGY

4.1. Data Collection

All data pertaining to 55 drowning cases in the district of Muzaffarnagar, India, spanning from 2017 to 2022, was obtained through the Right to Information (RTI) channel.

4.2. Data Analysis:

The collected data was organized and categorized using Microsoft Excel. The following parameters were analyzed:

- Gender of the victim (male, female, unidentified)
- Mode of drowning (accidental, suicidal, due to structural failure, homicidal, undetermined)
- Location of drowning (specific locations listed)
- Source of water bodies (canal, pond, undetermined)
- Police station-wise distribution of drowning cases in the district

4.3. Representation of Data:

The data was visually represented using 2D bar graphs in Microsoft Excel to facilitate clear interpretation of trends and patterns across the specified parameters.

4.4. Ethical Considerations:

- Prior consent was obtained from relevant authorities for accessing and utilizing the data.
- Confidentiality of individuals involved in the drowning incidents was strictly maintained throughout the study.

4.5. Limitations:

- The study relied on data obtained through the RTI channel, which may not encompass all drowning incidents in the district.
- The accuracy and completeness of the data are contingent upon the reliability of the sources and documentation.
- The retrospective nature of the study may introduce recall bias or incomplete information.
- Generalizability of the findings may be limited to the specific geographic context of Muzaffarnagar district.
- Factors influencing drowning incidents beyond the scope of the study, such as socioeconomic factors or environmental conditions, were not explored in depth.

5. RESULT

Figure 1: Gender Wise Distribution of Drowning Incidents by Mode

Figure 2: Representation Of Location Wise Drowning Incidents with Respect to Gender

Figure 3: Representation of total number of victims with respect to gender and source of water

cents, albeit to a lesser extent compared to males.

Figure 4: Total number of drowning cases in the district of Muzaffarnagar India from the year of 2017-2022

In **Figure 1**, examining drowning cases in Muzaffarnagar, several key observations emerge from the provided data:

5.1. Gender Specific Cases: Males appear to be disproportionately affected by drowning incidents, particularly in accidental and undetermined cases with males comprising the majority of victims (12 incidents compared to 2 incidents involving females). This suggests potential differences in behavior, exposure, or risk perception related to water activities between genders.

5.2. Undetermined Drowning Cases: Among undetermined drowning incidents, males are having 11 incidents compared to 5 involving females. Additionally, a notable number of drowning cases involve unidentified individuals (19 incidents).

5.3. Absence of Suicidal Drownings: There are no reported instances of suicidal drowning in the dataset.

5.4. Homicidal Drowning: The occurrence of homicidal drowning incident is involving 1 female.

In **Figure 2**, based on the provided data on drowning incidents, focusing on the gender distribution and occurrences of unidentified incidents, the following observations can be made:

5.5. Gender Specific Incidents:

Males are predominantly involved in drowning incidents across various locations, with varying numbers reported in different areas. Females are also involved in drowning inci-

5.6. Occurrences of Unidentified Incidents:

A significant number of drowning incidents are categorized as unidentified (21 incidents), indicating that the gender & location of the incident could not be determined. Among the unidentified incidents, there is a notable imbalance, with a higher number of incidents compared to the identified incidents.

5.7. Source-specific Trends:

Certain locations, such as Dhamaat canal, Ganga canal, and Canal balwakhedi and Rajwaha canal report more drowning incidents, involving both genders and, in some cases, unidentified incidents.

In **Figure 3**, based on the provided data on drowning cases in Muzaffarnagar, focusing on gender and the source of water, the observations are as follows:

5.8. Drowning in sources of water with respect to gender:

Canals: Males account for the highest number of drowning victims (21), followed by 7 females and 11 unidentified individuals.

Ponds: 3 males are reported as victims, while no females are recorded. However, 9 incidents remain unidentified.

Undetermined location: No male victims are recorded, while 1 female and 3 unidentified individuals are categorized under undetermined location.

5.9. Variation in gender-based drowning

Canals show the highest male drowning, followed by ponds and undetermined cases. Female involvement is relatively lower across all water sources.

In **Figure 4**, based on the provided data regarding drowning cases in Muzaffarnagar across different police stations from 2017 to 2022, the following observations can be made:

5.10. Varied Incidence Across Police Stations

The number of drowning cases varies significantly across different police stations. For instance, Bhopa and Charthawal have reported relatively higher numbers of cases compared to other stations.

5.11. Temporal Trends

There is notable variation in the number of cases reported over the years within each police station. i.e. Bhopa witnessed an increase in cases from 2018 to 2020 before experiencing a slight decline in 2021 and 2022. Conversely, Charthawal saw a fluctuating trend with peaks in 2018 and 2021 but relatively lower numbers in other years.

5.12. Stability and Fluctuations

Some police stations, like Sikhera and Chhapar, reported no drowning cases throughout the entire period under study, indicating either low incident rates or potential underreporting. In contrast, stations like Bhopa and Charthawal exhibit fluctuations in the number of cases, suggesting variations in local conditions, activities, or reporting practices.

6. DISCUSSION

The analysis of drowning cases in Muzaffarnagar district reveals a significant gender disparity, with males being disproportionately affected across various parameters. This observation is consistent with previous research conducted in different regions of India, such as Haryana and West Bengal, where males were also found to be more vulnerable to drowning incidents (Shubhendu et al., 2020; Thakar et al., 2018). The predominance of males in drowning cases suggests potential differences in behavior, exposure, or risk perception related to water activities between genders, as highlighted by (Isaac et al., 2007). Accidental drowning emerges as the leading cause of drowning incidents in Muzaffarnagar, aligning with findings from other studies conducted in Karnataka and Assam, which emphasized the preventable nature of such incidents (Kanchan et al., 2007; Teron & Paul, 2020). Canals, ponds, and other freshwater bodies constitute the primary locations where drowning incidents occur, underscoring the need for safety measures and interventions in these areas, as advocated by (Shetty & Shetty, 2007). The fluctuating trends in drowning cases across different police stations in Muzaffarnagar district highlight the dynamic nature of this public health issue. While certain stations, such as Bhopa and Charthawal, report relatively higher numbers of cases, others, like Sikhera and Chhapar, exhibit stability or no incidents at all over the study period. These variations may reflect differences in local conditions, activities, or reporting practices, as noted by (Gupta et al., 2020). The analysis also identifies several challenges and

opportunities for drowning prevention in Muzaffarnagar district. The significant number of unidentified drowning incidents underscores the need for improved documentation and reporting mechanisms to enhance data accuracy and completeness, as emphasized by (Dandona et al., 2019). Furthermore, the absence of suicidal drowning cases suggests potential underreporting or cultural factors influencing reporting behavior, warranting further investigation. The findings of (Siddiqui & Singh, 2022) regarding bucket-associated drowning in infants highlight the importance of tailored interventions targeting specific age groups and risk factors within the community.

7. CONCLUSION

The examination of drowning cases in Muzaffarnagar district highlights the necessity for thorough and focused strategies to mitigate drowning incidents and lessen the resulting morbidity and mortality. The significant gender disparity observed, with males being disproportionately affected, is consistent with findings from other regions of India and suggests the existence of gender-specific risk factors and behaviors related to water activities. Accidental drowning emerges as the leading cause of drowning incidents, highlighting the importance of preventive measures and safety interventions in high-risk areas such as canals and ponds. The fluctuating trends in drowning cases across different police stations emphasize the dynamic nature of this public health issue and the need for localized strategies informed by local conditions and activities. The challenges identified, including the significant number of unidentified drowning incidents and the absence of suicidal drowning cases, underscore the importance of improving data collection and reporting mechanisms and investigating cultural and contextual factors influencing reporting behavior. The findings underscore the critical role of multi-sectoral collaboration, public awareness campaigns, and evidence-based policy interventions in preventing drowning incidents. Initiatives such as the development of a national drowning prevention action plan by the National Disaster Response Force (NDRF) are essential steps towards creating a safer environment around water bodies and reducing the burden of drowning in Muzaffarnagar district and beyond (Ministry of Health and Family Welfare, 2023; The Print, 2024). By addressing the identified challenges and leveraging opportunities for intervention, stakeholders can work towards achieving the goal of eliminating preventable drowning deaths and ensuring the safety and well-being of communities.

8. Conflict of Interest

None

9. Acknowledgement

Authors are thankful to all

10. REFERENCES:

1. Armstrong, E. J., & Erskine, K. L. (2018). Investigation of drowning deaths: a practical review. *Academic Forensic Pathology*, 8(1), 8–43.
2. Dandona, R., Kumar, G. A., George, S., Kumar, A., & Dandona, L. (2019). Risk profile for drowning deaths in children in the Indian state of Bihar: results from a population-based study. *Injury Prevention*, 25(5), 364–371.
3. Gupta, M., Zwi, A. B., & Jagnoor, J. (2020). Opportunities for the development of drowning interventions in West Bengal, India: a review of policy and government programs. *BMC Public Health*, 20(1), 1–13.
4. Isaac, R., Helan, J., Minz, S., & Bose, A. (2007). Community perception of child drowning in South India: a qualitative study. *Annals of Tropical Paediatrics*, 27(3), 225–229.
5. Kanchan, T., Rastogi, P., & Mohanty, M. K. (2007). Profile of near drowning victims in a coastal region of Karnataka. *Journal of Indian Academy of Forensic Medicine*, 29(4), 52–54.
6. Lukaszuk, C., Ivers, R. Q., & Jagnoor, J. (2018). Systematic review of drowning in India: assessment of burden and risk. *Injury Prevention*, 24(6), 451–458.
7. McCall, J. D., & Sternard, B. T. (2017). Drowning.
8. Ministry of Health and Family Welfare. (2023, December 13). Strategic Framework for Drowning Prevention. <https://Pib.Gov.in/PressReleasePage.aspx?PRID=1985748#:~:Text=Promoting%20multi%2Dsectoral%20collaboration%2C%20strengthening,Action%20pillars%20for%20creating%20a>
9. Shetty, B. S. K., & Shetty, M. (2007). Epidemiology of drowning in Maangalore, a coastal Taluk of South India. *Journal of Forensic and Legal Medicine*, 14(7), 410–415.
10. Shubhendu, K., Singh, B., Kumar, R., Kumar, A., Chaudhary, A., & Kumari, S. (2020). Profile of Deaths Due to Drowning among Autopsies Conducted at Autopsy Center of Rajendra Institute of Medical Sciences, Ranchi. *Indian Journal of Forensic Medicine and Pathology*, 13(4).
11. Siddiqui, S. A., & Singh, M. V. (2022). Drowning in home environment: a little recognized mode of fatal injury in Indian infants and toddlers. *Indian Pediatrics*, 59(8), 659.
12. Teron, A., & Paul, B. (2020). A Study on the Patterns of Drowning Cases Brought for Medico-legal Autopsy. Prof. (Dr) RK Sharma, 20(4), 111.
13. Thakar, M. K., Luthra, D., & Khattar, J. S. (2018). Developing paradigms of drowning deaths in the State of Haryana, India. *Indian Police J*, 65(4), 48–57.
14. The Print. (2024, January 19). NDRF developing app, national plan to bring down number of drowning deaths, pegged at 38k a year. <https://Theprint.in/India/Ndrf-Developing-App-National-Plan-to-Bring-down-Number-of-Drowning-Deaths-Pegged-at-38k-a-Year/1930928/>.

